

Terpenoids. Part X. Synthesis of β -Bisabolene and Dipentene

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Through an application of the Wittig reaction with methyltriphenylphosphonium iodide on α -methyl- ϵ -keto- ϵ -(4-methyl- Δ^3 -cyclohexenyl)- Δ^3 -hexene and 4-methyl-1-acetyl- Δ^3 -cyclohexene, the latter constituting key intermediate in both the syntheses and prepared via an unambiguous route, the syntheses of β -bisabolene and dipentene have been accomplished.

In continuation of our synthetic studies¹ towards various terpenoids through an application of the Wittig reaction on appropriate ketones or diketones, syntheses of the title compounds have been achieved.

β -Bisabolene, a monocyclic sesquiterpene hydrocarbon, occurs widely in nature². The structure(I) has been assigned to it on the basis of chemical³ and physical³ studies and of its relationship with lanceol³ for which the structure is established⁴.

The present investigations record a clean synthesis of β -bisabolene through the following sequence of reactions.

4-Methyl-1-acetyl- Δ^3 -cyclohexene (IV), an important intermediate in the present scheme, was prepared in the pure form through deketalization⁵ of 4-methyl-1-(1', 1'-ethylenedioxyethyl)- Δ^3 -cyclohexene (III), which in turn was obtained via dehydration with PTS of the ketal-carbinol (II), the latter being prepared as reported in our earlier communication⁶.

1. Vig *et al.*, this *Journal*, 1965, 42, 773.
2. Simonsen, "The Terpenes", The University Press, Cambridge,⁶ Vol. III, 1952, p. 9.
3. Birch and Murray, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 1868.
4. Manjares *et al.*, *Tetrahedron*, 1964, 70, 333.
5. Church and Ireland, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1963, 28, 18.
6. Vig *et al.*, this *Journal*, 1965, 42, 581.

The ketone (IV) was characterized through its semicarbazone derivative, m.p. 154°, and its IR absorption spectrum which showed characteristic peaks⁷ at 1720 (C=O), 1435 (C-Me), 2900 (C-H band), 1165 cm⁻¹ (C-Me).

Literature⁸, however, reports the preparation of the ketone (IV) in admixture with the 3-methyl- Δ^1 -cyclohexene isomer.

The ketone (IV) was treated with diethyl carbonate in presence of sodium hydride to afford ethyl β -keto- β -(4-methyl- Δ^1 -cyclohexenyl)propionate (V) in 53.6% yield. The β -keto-ester (V) showed a positive ferric chloride test. Condensation of compound (V)

7. Cross, "Introduction to Practical I.R. Spectroscopy", Butterworth Scientific Publications, London, 1960, pp. 58-63.

8. Luis and Bailey, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1964, 86, 3999.

with γ -methyl- Δ^3 -butenyl bromide, prepared by addition of hydrogen bromide to isoprene, provided α -methyl- δ -ethoxycarbonyl- ϵ -keto- ϵ -(4-methyl- Δ^3 -cyclohexenyl)- Δ^3 -hexene (VI) in 62.2% yield. The β -keto-ester (VI) showed positive ferric chloride test. Alkaline hydrolysis of compound (VI), followed by distillation with copper powder, afforded α -methyl- ϵ -keto- ϵ -(4-methyl- Δ^3 -cyclohexenyl)- Δ^3 -hexene (VII) in 51.35% yield.

The ketone (VII), which was characterised through its IR absorption, showed peaks⁷ at 1720 (C=O), 1460 and 1380 (C-Me), 815 cm^{-1} (triply substituted double bond), was submitted to Wittig's reaction⁹ with methyltriphenylphosphonium iodide to afford the hydrocarbon (I) in 72.46% yield.

The identity of the synthetic hydrocarbon was established through comparison³ of its IR absorption spectrum which showed peaks⁷ at 1650, 890 ($\frac{R_1}{R_2} > C=CH_2$), 1380, 1400 (C-Me), 2900 (C-H band), 815 cm^{-1} (triply substituted double bond).

Since the ketone (IV) was prepared in the pure form, we repeated¹⁰ our experiments on this ketone with methyltriphenylphosphonium iodide in presence of methylsulphonyl carbanion, under nitrogen atmosphere, to obtain dipentene (VIII) in 77.5% yield.

The synthetic hydrocarbon (VIII) showed comparable¹¹ IR peaks at 1650, 890 ($\frac{R_1}{R_2} > C=CH_2$), 1380, 1435 (C-Me), 2900 cm^{-1} (C-H band).

EXPERIMENTAL

4-Methyl-1-(1', 1'-ethylenedioxyethyl)cyclohexan-4-ol (II) was prepared according to the procedure reported in an earlier communication⁶.

4-Methyl-1-(1', 1'-ethylenedioxyethyl)- Δ^3 -cyclohexene (III).—To the above ketal-carbinol (14.2 g.) were added *p*-toluenesulphonic acid (0.5 g.) and dry benzene (100 ml) and the contents were refluxed on a water bath for 4-5 hr. The reaction mixture was cooled and the excess of PTS was removed with 5% sodium bicarbonate solution. The organic layer was

*Melting points and boiling points are uncorrected. Microanalyses by Mr. B. N. Anand, Microanalyst, Punjab University Chemistry Department, Chandigarh. IR spectra were recorded on a Beckman I.R. 5 with sodium chloride optics, using a thin liquid film.

9. Greenwald *et al.*, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1963, 28, 1128.

10. Vig *et al.*, *this Journal*, 1964, 41, 142.

taken in ether, washed with water, and dried over sodium sulphate. After removal of the solvent, the residue was vacuum-distilled to afford (III), (9.7 g.) in 75.10% yield; b.p. $90^{\circ}/2-3$ mm, n_D^{20} 1.4720. (Found: C, 72.29; H, 10.00. $C_{11}H_{18}O_2$ requires C, 72.49; H, 9.96%.)

4-Methyl-1-acetyl- Δ^3 -cyclohexene (IV).—The above compound (9.5 g.) was treated with a mixture of acetone (100 ml) and HCl (25 ml, 10%) and kept at the room temperature for 2 hr. The contents after dilution with brine (100 ml) were worked up in the usual manner to furnish (IV, 5.9 g.) in 81.04% yield; b.p. $72.75^{\circ}/2-3$ mm, n_D^{20} 1.4700. (Found: C, 78.01; H, 10.34. $C_9H_{14}O$ requires C, 78.21; H, 10.21%.)

The semicarbazone, prepared in the usual manner and recrystallised from dilute ethanol, melted at 154° . Lit.¹¹ reports m.p. $157-157.5^{\circ}$ for 1-isomer. (Found: N, 21.20. $C_{10}H_{17}ON_3$ requires N, 21.53%.)

Ethyl β -Keto- β -(4-methyl- Δ^3 -cyclohexenyl)propionate (V).—To sodium hydride (3.5 g.) were added at the room temperature under nitrogen atmosphere and with stirring diethyl carbonate (7.0 g.) in anhydrous thiophene-free benzene (100 ml) and dimethyl formamide (15.5 g.). The temperature was raised to 60° and compound (IV) (4.7 g.) was added dropwise. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 2 hr. on a water bath. After cooling, it was poured on water and extracted with benzene. After removal of the solvent, the product was distilled under reduced pressure to afford (V) (3.8 g.) in 53.0% yield; b.p. $140-45^{\circ}/12$ mm, n_D^{20} 1.4750. This developed a violet colour with EtOH- $FeCl_3$. (Found: C, 68.75; H, 8.52. $C_{18}H_{28}O_3$ requires C, 68.54; H, 8.63%.)

α -Methyl- β -ethoxycarbonyl- ϵ -keto- ϵ -(4-methyl- Δ^3 -cyclohexenyl)- Δ^2 -hexene (VI).—To a cooled solution of *t*-butoxide [prepared from potassium metal (0.65 g.) and *t*-butanol 50 ml] was added compound (V) (3.4 g.) in *t*-butanol (10 ml). To the resulting potassium derivative was added dropwise, with external cooling, γ -methyl- Δ^2 -butenyl bromide (2.5 g.) and the mixture was refluxed for 10 hr. on the steam bath. Excess of *t*-butanol was removed under vacuum. Water was added to the residue and the organic layer was taken in ether and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. After removing the ether, the fraction distilling at $170-80^{\circ}/12$ mm was collected; yield 2.8 g. (82.22%), n_D^{20} 1.4830. This developed a violet colour with EtOH- $FeCl_3$ solution. (Found: C, 73.59; H, 9.10. $C_{17}H_{26}O_3$ requires C, 73.34; H, 9.41%.)

α -Methyl- ϵ -keto- ϵ -(4-methyl- Δ^3 -cyclohexenyl)- Δ^2 -hexene (VII).—Compound (VI) (2.5 g.) was refluxed with a mixture of KOH (1.75 g.), water (15 ml) and methanol (30 ml) for 10 hr. Methanol was removed under reduced pressure and the residue after cooling was acidified with HCl (dil.). The organic material was extracted with ether and dried. After evaporating the solvent, the residue was mixed with copper powder (0.2 g.) and heated to $160-70^{\circ}$ in an oil bath. The ketone (VII) came over at $128-30^{\circ}/2-3$ mm; yield 0.95 g. (51.35%), n_D^{20} 1.5030. (Found: C, 81.78; H, 10.62. $C_{14}H_{22}O$ requires C, 81.50; H, 10.76%.)

α -Methyl- α -methylene- ϵ -(4-methyl- Δ^3 -cyclohexenyl)- Δ^2 -hexene (I).—A solution of sodium methylsulphinyl carbanion was prepared under nitrogen from sodium

11. Bordwell, "Organic Chemistry", The Macmillan Co., New York, 1963, p. 284.

12. Neves, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1948, 31, 45.

hydride (0.35 g.) and dimethyl sulphoxide (6 ml). The solution was cooled in ice-cold water and stirred during addition of methyltriphenylphosphonium iodide (2.0 g.) in dimethyl sulphoxide (12.5 ml) when the reddish colour of the methylenephosphorane was produced. After stirring at the room temperature for 15 min., the compound (VII) (0.7 g.) in THF (10 ml) was added and stirring continued for 2 hr. at 50°. The reaction mixture was cooled and poured on cold water (20 ml). The organic layer was taken in petroleum (40-60°) and washed thrice with cold water. After removal of the solvent, the residue was vacuum-distilled to provide (1.05 g.) 72.46% yield; b.p. 100-105°/2-3 mm., n_D^{20} 1.5090. (Found: C, 88.00; H, 11.75. $C_{10}H_{16}$ requires C, 88.16; H, 11.84%).

4-Methyl-1-isopropenyl- Δ^3 -cyclohexene (VIII)—Methylenephosphorane was prepared under nitrogen atmosphere from sodium hydride (0.30 g.), dimethyl sulphoxide (3.5 ml); and methyltriphenylphosphonium iodide (3 g.) in dimethyl sulphoxide (7.2 ml) in the manner as in (I). To this was added the ketone (IV) (0.5 g.) in THF (7 ml). After working up as in the case of (I), the residual oil was distilled under reduced pressure to provide (VIII) in 0.38 g. yield (77.5%); b.p. 55°/2-3 mm, n_D^{20} 1.4850. (Found: C, 88.10; H, 11.70. $C_{10}H_{16}$ requires C, 88.16; H, 11.84%).

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